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INTRODUCTION

- The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) first emerged in December 2019 in Wuhan City, Hubei, China, following reports of several pneumonia cases with unknown aetiology agent.
- Roughly 19.5 million infections and more than 700,000 deaths have been reported worldwide by the early of August 2020.
- Remdesivir is a nucleotide analogue which inhibits viral RNA polymerase and consequently disrupts viral replication.
- This drug also has broad antiviral activities.
- Remdesivir has been demonstrated to possess prophylactic and therapeutic activity against MERS-CoV in a rhesus-macaque model with lower viral replication and lung damage and the eventual improved clinical symptoms.

OBJECTIVE

- This review aims to summarise and synthesise published data evaluating remdesivir and COVID-19. Our primary aim is the effect and safety of remdesivir among COVID-19 patients.

METHOD

- 01 Identifying research questions
- 02 Identifying relevant studies
- 03 Study selection
- 04 Charting the data
- 05 Collating, summarizing and reporting the results

RESULTS

Fig.1: The PRISMA flowchart for the included studies of remdesivir for the treatment of COVID-19.

Fig.2: Type of studies and country of origin of 13 included studies.

CONCLUSIONS

- We found a paucity of high-quality clinical trials in relation to in-vitro, in-vivo and non-randomised studies, and so the quality of evidence to inform clinical practice is still not strong.
- The current evidence-base needs to be consolidated with the publication of more clinical trials with bigger cumulative samples, to the point where optimal information size is reached.
- Due to insufficient data, we are unable to determine further the applicability of the findings to all COVID patients, that is, adults and children.
- The high percentage of adverse effects in RCTs among adults and children need to be investigated further.

Table 1: Summary of findings of the 13 included studies.

Type of Study, Author(s), Year	Key Findings
Case reports/series Holshue et al. (2020) Hillaker et al. (2020) Kujawski et al. (2020) Lescure et al. (2020)	Total number of patients: 10 All patients showed improvement in conditions after at least 24 hours of treatment with remdesivir.
Cross-sectional Elfiky (2020) Zhang & Zhou (2020) Yin et al. (2020) Gordon et al. (2020)	All studies reported the effectiveness of remdesivir in triphosphosphate form binding to the new coronavirus strain RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp).
In vitro Wang et al. (2020) Choy et al. (2020)	Remdesivir is one of the drugs that was found to inhibit SARS-CoV-2 replication in Vero E6 cells with EC50 under 100 µM.
Randomised-controlled trial Grein et al. (2020) Wang et al. (2020)	Total number of patients: 61 (8 excluded) 36 patients (68%) had an improvement in oxygen-support class (17 of them were extubated). 25 patients (47%) were discharged. 7 patients (13%) passed away. Total number of patients: 237 (158 received remdesivir; 79 received placebo) Time to clinical improvement not significant (Hazard Ratio (HR) 1.23 [95% CI 0.87–1.75]). Patients receiving remdesivir within 10 days of symptom onset has a statistically faster time to clinical improvement (HR 1.52 [0.95–2.43]). Adverse effects were reported in between 60% and 66% of patients in both studies.
In vivo Williamson et al. (2020)	Involved 2 groups of rhesus macaques (remdesivir and control groups). Reduction of pulmonary infiltration in the remdesivir-treated group showed in radiographs. Viral loads reduced in the remdesivir-treated group but not statistically significant. Virus titre in bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) of the remdesivir-treated group reduced around 100-fold after 12 hours of treatment.

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